

A Comprehensive Survey and Taxonomy of Cybersecurity Challenges and Proactive Measures for IoT

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The use of Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) in various domains is continuously increasing. The benefits offered by UAVs enable the facilitation of functions or execution of tasks, such as search and rescue, which would otherwise be challenging or financially restrictive. Furthermore, UAVs are important for the military domain being considered as efficient weapons. Therefore, many countries and retail companies are investing in the massive production of UAVs for market as well as government purposes. Nevertheless, most UAVs in all domains, lack even basic cybersecurity mechanisms, thus, posing cybersecurity threats that significantly affect cybersecurity aspects or result in physical damage and even loss of human life. Many cybersecurity solutions have been proposed in the literature, encompassing both reactive and proactive measures, with the

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latter being preferable. Added to this, threat modeling emerges as an effective proactive measure with minimal cost and complexity.

The current work conducts extensive and comprehensive research concerning the domain of UAVs. Initially, the article outlines the historical development of UAVs and the different taxonomies in which they are classified according to different characteristics (e.g., number of rotors). The next sections detail a comprehensive description of the Internet of Drones (IoD) environment and the various relevant cybersecurity issues. Subsequently, the article examines a wide range of diverse threat modeling approaches found in the literature, while it categorizes relevant articles based on whether they describe solutions that integrate threat modeling or propose novel approaches for threat modeling.

CCS Concepts: • **General and reference** → **Surveys and overviews**; • **Computer systems organization** → *Embedded and cyber-physical systems*; • **Networks** → **Network types**; • **Security and privacy** → **Security requirements**; *Formal security models*; **Systems security**; **Network security**;

Additional Key Words and Phrases: Internet Of Drones (IoD), IoD architecture, unmanned aerial vehicles, internet of things (IoT), drones, cybersecurity, security vulnerabilities, taxonomy, proactive cybersecurity, threat modeling

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1 Introduction

Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) are rapidly expanding due to their numerous applications and their ability to incorporate into existing domains (e.g., search and rescue) as well as new technological advances. There are various laudable applications for UAVs including government (e.g., military, maritime, and coastal monitoring), private sector (e.g., payload delivery surveillance) as well as civilian applications (e.g., cinematography, agriculture). The majority of UAVs applications concern government applications and most investments originate from governments [74]. It is estimated that the global market for small UAVs is expected to reach \$4.1B annually in 2024 [48], while at the same time, according to Laraib et al. [65], is expected to reach \$2.342.1 million by 2028, with a **compound annual growth rate (CAGR)** of 25.08%. At the same time, some reports estimate that the global market of small UAVs will reach \$10.04 billion by 2030.¹ Many countries such as China are developing their own UAVs for military use as well as for the public market [58]. In the latter case, UAVs are preferred as means for many tasks such as search and tracking operations as a result of their lower cost and ability to operate even in harsh environments [4, 78, 109, 110]. Specifically, regarding cost, a UAV for simple use can start from around \$60 (e.g., Parrot Rolling Spider Drone Mini²) while professional UAVs can cost more than \$16,500 (e.g., DJI Inspire 3³) which is still cheaper than other vehicles such as helicopters. Among the most common military missions of UAVs are reconnaissance, border patrol, and **Chemical-Biological-Radiological-Nuclear (CBRN)** detection [59]. Countries such as France, China, and the USA are known as the top suppliers for these types of UAVs. Furthermore, concerning the market sector, many retail giants of UAVs have expressed their interest in the market of UAVs including companies such as Walmart, Amazon, Google, and more [78]. Another sector widely used is to monitor **Critical**

¹<https://www.marketsandmarkets.com/Market-Reports/small-uav-market-141134567.html>

²<https://www.parrot.com/en/support/documentation/rolling-spider>

³<https://store.dji.com/gr/product/dji-inspire-3?vid=136551>

Infrastructures (CIs) and for monitoring pipelines (oil, gas etc.) in harsh environments such as in Alaska. These are expensive as they can operate for weeks or even more.

Nevertheless, while UAVs are used in various domains to facilitate different tasks, they pose the risk of being hacked by malicious actors and used for malicious purposes [51]. UAV systems are susceptible to attacks that could target the cyber elements, physical elements, the wireless link, or other critical components of the system [53]. Compromised UAVs can be utilized to perform malicious activities ranging from attacks that violate privacy (e.g., taking pictures in secret, monitoring a person without its consent) [99] up to attacks that cause physical damage and/or even death (e.g., kamikaze attacks) [21]. Furthermore, malicious actors could capture UAVs and retrieve the stored media, resulting in the violation of the **Confidentiality, Integrity, Availability (CIA)** Triad principles including the retrieval of media that the UAV has acquired or the coordinates of the areas where the UAV has operated or even taking control of a target UAV.

UAVs rely on different sensors to make critical calculations such as their flight attitude, which means a possible attack could lead to unexpected behavior or even a crash of the device. Furthermore, the environment in which they operate, referred to as the **Internet of Drones (IoD)**, is also exposed to attacks, such as drone capture and **Man in the Middle (MiTM)** attacks [11, 57]. Similar to other systems, UAVs utilize communication protocols for their remote operation. The most prevalent protocol used for the communication between **Ground Control Stations (GCSs)** and UAVs, is the **Micro Air Vehicle Link (MAVLink)**⁴ [13]. It is used in different types of UAVs and is supported by two of the dominant autopilot systems, namely Ardupilot⁵ and PX4⁶ [60]. Despite the advantages of the MAVLink protocol which is considered a lightweight open-source and cross-platform solution, it is exposed to different attacks including spoofing, MiTM, message forgery and **Denial of Service (DoS)** [13, 60].

In case of being compromised, UAVs as well as the other components of an IoD system could result in serious consequences, involving physical damage to buildings or loss of human lives. Consequently, there is intense active research toward the implementation of effective measures to either enhance the cybersecurity of the IoD devices or defend against UAV attacks by detecting and neutralizing the targeted devices (i.e., anti-drone measures). With regard to the cybersecurity enhancement of the devices, there are two major categories of approaches. The implemented measures can be either reactive or proactive.

Considering the energy consumption restrictions of UAVs and other IoD devices, proactive measures are preferred over reactive measures, since they are not required to be implemented on the devices [51]. Thus, the cost and complexity of safeguarding the IoD system are reduced while at the same time, the cybersecurity capabilities are enhanced. Threat modeling emerges as a promising proactive solution, providing implementations with low cost and without limitation by the aforementioned restrictions of UAV devices.

The current work advances the domain of UAVs through thorough and expansive research. Specifically, the study aims at studying various cybersecurity threats that affect UAVs and the IoD environment in general, as well as the proposed cybersecurity solutions, especially threat modeling. In this regard, a substantial portion of the study is dedicated to exploring the Internet of IoD environment, shedding light on its complexities, cybersecurity requirements, and challenges. This is particularly pertinent as the IoD represents a relatively uncharted territory. Furthermore, the survey conducts a critical synthesis of various threat modeling approaches found in existing literature, distinguishing between those that incorporate threat modeling into existing solutions

⁴<https://mavlink.io/en/>

⁵<https://ardupilot.org/>

⁶<https://px4.io/>

and those proposing new methodologies. This categorization clarifies the current landscape while also paving the way for future research, potentially inspiring innovative approaches to threat modeling in UAV security. Overall, the main contributions of this survey are:

- Comprehensive analysis of the IoD environment, including architectures, network characteristics, cybersecurity requirements, cybersecurity issues, and cybersecurity measures.
- Novel comprehensive taxonomy of cybersecurity attacks affecting different layers of an IoD system (i.e., hardware, software, and network).
- Comprehensive survey of IoD security measures.
- Novel taxonomy of threat modeling methodologies.

Previous surveys have extensively examined security and privacy issues across UAV and IoT ecosystems. Gharibi et al. [41] introduced foundational concepts and a layered IoD architecture, laying the groundwork for later studies. Arteaga et al. [21] focused on GPS-spoofing and cyber-vulnerabilities of individual UAVs but did not address broader IoD infrastructures. Yaacoub et al. [109] analysed UAV security threats and mitigations; however, their scope centred on isolated drone platforms rather than integrated IoD systems.

The survey conducted by Haider et al. [45] advanced the discussion by exploring IoD routing algorithms and associated cybersecurity challenges but did not extensively examine proactive cybersecurity measures or threat modeling. Furthermore, the review by Haidar et al. [44], while thorough, focused primarily predominantly on pseudonymity in **Cooperative Intelligent Transport Systems (C-ITS)** and did not directly explore comprehensive IoD environments. Abdelmaboud [4] provided valuable IoD requirements and taxonomies, though cybersecurity and formal threat modeling were only partially covered.

Alzahrani et al. [18] delivered a comprehensive overview of UAV applications and security challenges but does not explicitly consider IoD-specific infrastructures and lacks detailed IoD-specific infrastructure analysis and study of cybersecurity threat modeling. Adil et al. [6] (IEEE T-ITS 2023) presented a taxonomy of UAV-aided IoT threats, but did not include full IoD architectures and proactive threat modeling methodologies.

Domain-specific works such as Wang, Liu, and Song [106] focused on Counter-UAS detection and mitigation, while Gohari et al. [42] provided a systematic review of surveillance drones in smart cities—both descriptive rather than prescriptive. Alsamhi and Ma [15] addressed drone applications in smart-city environments with limited security depth. Most recently, Algarni and Jan [11] introduced pSLAPS-IoD, a privacy-aware lightweight authentication protocol, representing a proactive defence at protocol level but could not be considered a holistic taxonomy.

In contrast, the current survey significantly expands upon existing literature by explicitly focusing on the cybersecurity landscape of IoD, introducing detailed and structured taxonomies of cybersecurity threats across multiple layers (software, hardware, network), and comprehensively evaluating proactive cybersecurity measures, particularly highlighting threat modeling techniques explicitly suited for IoD. The approach presented in this work bridges crucial gaps in previous works by delivering a uniquely integrated view that addresses specific IoD vulnerabilities, proactive cybersecurity frameworks, and state-of-the-art threat modeling practices.

Consequently, the contributions of this survey are multifaceted, enhancing theoretical understanding and offering a foundation for practical advancements in the secure integration of UAVs into different application domains. In particular, this work provides the first end-to-end synthesis that couples a layered IoD taxonomy with actionable threat modeling and proactive cyber-defence guidance.

The unique contributions of this survey are contextualized in Table 1, which contrasts it with key peer-reviewed surveys published between 2019 and 2025.

Table 1. Comparative Analysis of UAV/IoD Security Surveys

Survey / Article	Year	UAV Security	IoD-specific Focus	Multi-layer Taxonomy	Threat Modeling Analysis	Proactive Cybersecurity
Gharibi et al.	2016	✓	✓	×	×	×
Arteaga et al.	2019	✓	×	×	×	✓ (partial)
Haidar et al.	2019	✓	× (C-ITS focus)	×	×	✓ (limited)
Yaacoub et al.	2020	✓	×	×	×	✓ (partial)
Alzahrani et al.[18]	2020	✓	×	×	×	×
Abdelmaboud	2021	✓	✓	✓ (partial)	×	×
Yahuza et al.	2021	✓	✓	✓ (partial)	×	×
Adil et al.	2023	✓	~	✓ (partial)	×	×
Haider et al.	2022	✓	✓	×	×	×
Gohari et al.	2022	✓	×	×	×	×
Wang, Liu, and Song	2021	✓	~ (C-UAS)	✓	×	✓ (strong)
Omolara et al.	2023	✓	~	×	×	×
Algarni and Jan[12]	2024	✓	✓	×	×	✓ (auth.)
This Survey	2025	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

Legend: ✓ = fully covered; ✓ (partial) = partially covered; ~ = tangential focus; × = not covered.

The remainder of this article is organized as follows: Section 2 describes the research methodology, including the systematic selection of literature and the keyword strategy. Section 3 presents the IoD environment, detailing both the fundamental IoD architecture and variations proposed in recent literature. Section 4 analyses the cybersecurity requirements for IoT and IoD, and includes a comparative overview of international regulatory frameworks. Section 5 discusses the cybersecurity issues affecting IoD and IoT systems, introducing a comprehensive taxonomy of attacks across software, hardware, and network layers. This section also provides in-depth coverage of ransomware and DoS attacks, and examines their unique impact within IoD environments. Section 6 surveys key security mechanisms in IoT and IoD, with particular emphasis on emerging solutions based on **Artificial Intelligence (AI)** and blockchain technology. The section further examines the tradeoffs between security and operational efficiency in practical IoD deployments. Section 7 provides a categorization and critical evaluation of threat modeling and threat assessment approaches, analysing their applicability to IoD and highlighting both established and novel methodologies. Finally, Section 8 summarizes the key lessons learned and outlines directions for future research.

2 Research Methodology

2.1 Research Questions

The main objective of the current work is to describe the various cybersecurity threats that affect UAVs and the IoD environment as well as the proposed cybersecurity solutions, especially threat modeling. Therefore, the following research questions have been defined to guide the research process.

- **RQ1:** What are the characteristics and cybersecurity requirements of UAVs and IoD?
- **RQ2:** What are the cybersecurity and privacy issues of UAVs and IoD?
- **RQ3:** Which risk assessment and threat modeling approaches are proposed to combat the cybersecurity and privacy issues of UAVs and IoD?
- **RQ4:** Are there existing taxonomies for threat modeling approaches?
- **RQ5:** How could this study apply to real-life scenarios concerning UAV applications?

2.2 Literature Research Process

The current work aims at providing a survey concerning the latest cybersecurity concerns and threat modeling approaches of UAVs and the IoD domain. Aiming at providing a comprehensive assessment including the latest proposed approaches, the research scope of this article is within the year range of 2019 - 2025 while there are also references to published articles from previous years which are considered critical for the conducted research. The searched keywords necessarily include either the terms UAV, drone or IoD. To ensure comprehensive retrieval of relevant literature and

avoid bias arising from terminological variation, the search strategy necessarily includes both the terms “drone” and “UAV”. In particular, The terms “drone” and “UAV” are often used interchangeably, but their usage varies significantly across different communities. “UAV” is generally favoured in scientific and technical literature, while “drone” is more commonly found in mainstream media and commercial contexts. The inclusion of both keywords is important because academic databases and indexing systems often treat “drone” and “UAV” as distinct terms. Restricting searches to only one can result in missing relevant articles indexed under the other. Therefore, this approach reflects the diverse and evolving language used across academic, industrial, and policy-oriented sources. For reasons of clarity and simplicity, in this article, the terms “drone” and “UAV” are used interchangeably. Furthermore, the keyword set is expanded to include terms such as threat assessment model and threat modeling. The complete list of keywords that have been used as search criteria in various scientific databases, is presented in Table ST1 in Appendix A in the electronic supplementary material, while the research methodology is described in Figure 1. The total number in of included studies in Figure 1 accounts for citations from both the main sections of this survey as well as the supplementary material.

The inclusion of keywords that appear to be subsets or close variations of one another, such as “Drone threat model” and “Drone threat assessment model,” is a conscious and purposeful aspect of the research design. In academic publishing, authors and indexing services frequently use slightly different terms to describe similar concepts. If only a single keyword were used, there is a significant risk that relevant studies could be missed. By incorporating a broader set of related terms, the search strategy ensures that the review captures as much relevant literature as possible, including studies that might not be retrieved by narrower searches.

Small differences in keyword phrasing, for example, the addition of words like “assessment” or the use of quotation marks, can influence which results are returned in academic databases. Including both more general and more specific terms helps to guarantee that the review is comprehensive and representative of the field. This strategy also enhances the transparency and reproducibility of the research, making it possible for others to follow the same approach and achieve similar results. Adopting such a method aligns with the recommendations found in systematic review guidelines.

2.3 Data Sources

The selected keywords have been queried against trusted peer-reviewed data sources including: ACM Digital Library,⁷ IEEE Xplore Digital Library,⁸ Science Direct,⁹ Springer Link,¹⁰ Google Scholar,¹¹ and others.

2.4 Review and Evaluation Process

In order to assess each identified research article in terms of its relevance to the target scope of this work, a well-defined methodology was applied which consists of four sequential phases, namely, (i) Identification, (ii) Screening, (iii) Eligibility, and (iv) Inclusion. Each phase includes assessment steps that might result in the exclusion of several studies (i.e., research articles) if they don’t meet the inclusion criteria.

Initially, during the *Identification* phase, a domain-specific corpus of search keywords pertinent to IoD cybersecurity was systematically compiled. The set of keywords is presented in Table ST1 in Appendix A. Subsequently, the keywords have been queried against well-known and peer-reviewed

⁷<https://dl.acm.org/>

⁸<https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/Xplore/home.jsp>

⁹<https://www.sciencedirect.com/>

¹⁰<https://link.springer.com/>

¹¹<https://scholar.google.com>

Fig. 1. Research methodology.

databases such as IEEE Xplore, and ACM Digital Library, as well as search engines such as Google Scholar. Furthermore, the results were further filtered by excluding research articles which are published earlier than 2019 (i.e., 6-year period filtering) as well as research articles which are not written in English. Nevertheless, significant articles that have been published earlier than 2019, have been included.

During the *Screening* phase, the remaining studies have been subjected to screening based on their title and abstract. In particular, each research article has been reviewed to identify those that are not relevant based on their title and abstract text. The research articles that have been deemed relevant were subsequently reviewed in terms of their contents to exclude articles that do not fit within the scope of this work. Following the title and abstract screening, the studies are further assessed based on their introduction and conclusions section where those that are considered irrelevant are excluded resulting in a reduced amount of studies.

Concerning the *Eligibility* phase, the research articles that have successfully passed the Screening phase are carefully studied concerning the ability to answer any of the research questions that have been defined earlier in this work. Specifically, each research article undergoes a full-text review to determine the aspects that they are addressing. The studies that do not address AI or **Machine Learning (ML)** in cybersecurity or the concept of either manual or dynamic cybersecurity taxonomies, are deemed irrelevant and are excluded from the set of research articles.

Finally, the *Inclusion* phase includes the final set of research articles that have been used to conduct the survey in this work. The final set consists of the articles that have met all the inclusion criteria from all the previous phases.

Fig. 2. IoD architecture layers.

Fig. 3. IoD architecture.

3 Internet of Drones Environment

The **Internet of Things (IoT)** is defined as a network of physical objects, namely “Things”, that are equipped with sensor devices, processing ability, specific software, also including other relevant technologies used for exchanging data over the Internet. IoD derives its name from the IoT by replacing the word Things with UAVs [32]. IoD is considered a specialized version of IoT that enables the coordination of UAVs. Practically, the integrated devices and sensors on a UAV, are smart IoT devices [99].

The term IoD was first introduced in Gharibi et al. [41] which defined IoD as a layered network control architecture designed for facilitating the coordination of UAVs in terms of accessing the controlled airspace and providing navigation services. The architecture of IoD is based on three large-scale network schemes, namely **Air Traffic Control (ATC)**, cellular networks, and the Internet. Furthermore, IoD is described as a layered architecture that consists of five distinct layers each layer can access either the previous or the next layer. The five layers of the IoD architecture are illustrated in Figure 2. The implementation of a layered architecture provides various advantages including separation of concerns, scalability, code maintainability, and flexibility in terms of modifying a layer without requiring major modifications in the other layers.

3.1 IoD Architecture

The first-ever IoD architecture has been proposed by Gharibi et al. [41]. Since the first mention of the IoD architecture, there have been many different approaches pertaining to the modeling of a network that consists of UAVs. The initial IoD architecture comprises different components that regulate the operation of UAVs. Figure 3 depicts the architecture of IoD as given in [14]. In particular, the components include Airspace, **Zone Service Providers (ZSPs)**, Zones, Communication, UAVs/UAVs, and External Systems and are detailed as follows:

Fig. 4. Structure of an IoD zone [41].

Airspace: Airspace is the area in which UAVs operate. The concept of the airspace is similar to road networks. Airspace is divided into separate zones, each zone into airways, intersections (made by at least two airways), and nodes (i.e., target point). The movement of UAVs is strictly allowed only within the elements of each zone (i.e., airways, intersections, nodes).

Zone Service Providers (ZSPs): They constitute the entity that is responsible for regulating the operation of UAVs within the designated zone. ZSPs provide navigation information between any two nodes to the requesting UAVs [41].

Zones: The airspace is partitioned into zones that are under authority of one or multiple ZSPs. Each zone is partitioned into four elements:

- (1) Airways are paths similar to land roads.
- (2) Intersections are points formed by two or more intersecting airways.
- (3) Nodes are defined as points of interest that can be reached by crossing a chain of air-way and intersection elements [41]. Nodes are the take-off and landing points of UAVs.
- (4) Gates are special points that connect adjacent zones and are categorized into inbound or outbound.

Communication: Cloud-based communication infrastructure that enables communication of two components within the IoD environment.

UAVs/UAVs: UAVs are the main nodes of IoD and have to meet specific requirements in order to avoid collision and successfully complete their mission [14].

External Systems: There are third-party systems (e.g., weather service providers) that facilitate the efficient operation of an IoD system. The general structure of a zone in the IoD architecture is shown in Figure 4 while a more detailed illustration of the zone (including airways, intersections, and nodes) is depicted in Figure 5. The navigation of UAVs in airways and intersections is regulated according to the designated direction. On the other hand, there are no restrictions within nodes, thus allowing UAVs to operate in a free flight mode [41].

Recently, many researchers have proposed various IoD architectures based on different technologies such as cloud and IoT. Whilst each architecture leverages different technologies, cybersecurity remains a top priority in all proposed architectures. Aggarwal et al. [9] proposed the utilization of blockchain to store the data that has been gathered by UAVs and subsequently update the content into the distributed ledgers in order to ensure the cybersecurity and privacy of the IoD network.

Bera et al. [24] proposed another architecture that is based on the concept of IoT. In their work, the authors consider a variety of IoT smart devices (i.e., sensors) shrunk onto a single device [110]. In particular the architecture implements the connection between UAVs that are located within the operation zone, UAVs and **Ground Station Server (GSS)**, as well as in the middle of GSS and the **Control Room (CR)**.

Fig. 5. Elements within an IoD zone based on [41].

A **Mobile Edge Computing (MEC)** based IoD approach can provide reliability in terms of communication within the IoD network and is proposed by Yahuza et al. [110]. Specifically, the proposed architecture consists of four distinct components. The first entity concerns the server instance that enables setting up authentication before communication between UAVs. The second entity includes mobile MEC devices that facilitate faster communication between UAVs located outside their flying zone. The GCS is the third entity that is responsible for communication with the flying UAVs' corresponding MECs to exchange mission-relevant information including control messages. The flying UAVs at the different flying zones constitute the fourth entity.

3.2 IoD Network

UAVs operate within a special type of **Mobile Ad-Hoc Networks (MANETs)** that is formed with a group of flying UAVs, called **Flying Ad hoc Networks (FANET)** [66, 85]. FANET stands for Flying Ad Hoc Networks, and it represents a subclass of MANETs specifically designed for the use of UAVs [66]. In particular FANET leverages methodologies similar to MANET and **Vehicular Ad-hoc Network (VANET)**[66].

These networks are characterized by their high mobility, scalability, and robustness, which make them suitable for dynamic and scalable infrastructures. FANETs are independent wireless networks that allow UAVs to communicate with each other and with ground control stations without the need for a centralized infrastructure. In a FANET network, the path of each drone is unpredictable, leading to constant changes in the connections between them. Data is transmitted through a network where drones relay information to one another, ultimately connecting back to a ground station.

The simplest FANET architecture is illustrated in Figure 6 where UAVs have the capability to interact with each other without relying on established ground network infrastructure. Specifically, UAVs perform two main functionalities: (i) establish **UAV-to-UAV (U2U)** connections with adjacent UAVs to gather data and information and (ii) subsequently transmit the gathered data to the GCS through a **UAV to Infrastructure (U2I)** communication link.

They are particularly useful in scenarios where rapid deployment and reconfiguration of network topology are required, such as in disaster response situations. The main challenges for FANETs include dealing with the limited flight time of UAVs and finding routing protocols that can support the network dynamics due to the high mobility of the nodes [81].

Fig. 6. Simple FANET architecture.

3.3 International Regulatory Frameworks and Comparative Compliance Adaptations

The increasing integration of UAVs into civil and commercial airspace has resulted in a variety of national regulatory practices. Major jurisdictions, including the United States, the European Union, China, the United Kingdom, Australia, and Japan, apply distinct rules governing registration, operational categories, airspace permissions, geofencing measures, and cybersecurity-related oversight. These variations reflect differing regulatory priorities and underlying risk-management orientations. Due to space limitations, the detailed comparative analysis is provided in Appendix B.

4 Cybersecurity Issues of IoD Systems

While UAVs are used in various applications in many countries, they are susceptible to a variety of cyber-attacks and are often targeted by attackers [65, 82]. UAVs include different integrated parts which basically constitute smart IoT devices and therefore, they inherit many cybersecurity issues of IoT [25, 77]. The integrated devices include among others thermal infrared imaging cameras, GPS, satellite-based navigation systems, speed sensors and altitude sensors. Each device gathers specific data which are either processed by the UAV or sent to GCS for further analysis and different calculations.

IoD introduces distinct operational constraints, cybersecurity challenges and solutions, consequently distinguishing it significantly from traditional systems [41, 45, 109]. In order to utilize all available capabilities of IoD these issues need to be considered and addressed properly. The specific limitations and challenges of IoD are:

- **Lack of inherent security:** Lack of security by design approach implementation during development.
- **Battery Life:** Drones have limited flight times due to battery constraints, which can limit their range and endurance.
- **Payload Capacity:** The ability to carry weight is limited, affecting the type and number of sensors or additional equipment a drone can carry.
- **Air Traffic Management:** Integrating drones into existing air traffic without causing disruptions or safety hazards is a complex challenge.
- **Interference:** Drones operating in urban environments may face signal interference from various sources, impacting their communication capabilities.
- **Regulatory Compliance:** Adhering to evolving regulations and standards for drone operations can be difficult, especially across different jurisdictions.

- **Privacy:** Drones can inadvertently infringe on privacy if they capture images or data from private properties without consent. Consequently, ensuring the security of the data collected and transmitted by drones is paramount, particularly in sensitive applications.
- **Network Scalability:** As the number of drones increases, managing network traffic and avoiding congestion becomes more challenging. Implementing efficient routing minimizes the risk of possible collision and contributes toward limiting energy consumption, thus enabling increased up-time and coverage.

During the last years, many researchers have studied the cybersecurity of IoD systems and UAVs in particular. Given that IoD is considered a sub-part of IoT, it shares similar properties to IoT [110]. IoD networks are utilized in applications such as search and rescue and civilian monitoring while the data is exchanged over an insecure wireless network [47, 58, 60, 78, 109, 110]. The data that is exchanged may contain critical information along with personal data of the operator such as the name or the geographical coordinates of the operator's house [11]. IoD is vulnerable to many attacks such as man-in-the-middle, impersonation and password-guessing attacks. Cybersecurity is a primary concern of IoD since the use of wireless communication links may expose the IoD environment to several cybersecurity as well as privacy threats.

Furthermore, UAVs and relevant equipment (i.e., sensor nodes) are often installed in hostile or unattended environments where the continuous monitoring of the devices is not possible. Therefore, UAVs are further exposed to physical cybersecurity risks (e.g., an adversary could steal the deployed sensors and perform physical hacking) [55, 87]. Furthermore, the attacker could leverage the extracted information from the stolen equipment to manufacture attacker nodes and deploy them in the existing network [87]. It is important to clarify that the cybersecurity issues in this case do not concern the action of the attacker but rather the impact they entail. Another notable example of such a case is the case of the American UAV on 4th December 2011 near the city of Kashmar [17, 63]. The American UAV has allegedly violated the Iranian airspace and has been successfully captured (i.e., landed) by jamming the satellite signals, followed by a GPS spoofing attack [17, 63].

4.1 IoD Cybersecurity Requirements

Cybersecurity requirements are defined in all systems in order to ensure the proper operation of the network as well as safeguard the entire infrastructure against various cyber-attacks. Many researchers have studied the different requirements of IoT and IoD systems in terms of communications and cybersecurity [65, 107]. The consequences of a possible cyber-attack that violates any of these requirements range from changing the path of a UAV to communication interference which could also result in the crash of the affected UAV. Therefore, compliance with these requirements must be ensured.

UAVs are mostly employed for critical tasks such as search and rescue operations in hard-to-reach areas, surveillance, and delivery of important items (e.g., medical equipment). Therefore, it is vital to ensure that the communication requirements are met. Furthermore, the support for real-time and remote communications has been defined as another critical requirement that enables issuing remotely time-based commands and control instructions concerning flight status reports in real-time. Concerning surveillance applications, it is required to maintain a high uplink data rate connection from the UAV to the GCS in order to send **High-Definition (HD)** video and images without delay or packet loss [111].

With regard to cybersecurity requirements, the main target is to increase the level of cybersecurity and privacy. In particular, cybersecurity, safety, and privacy preservation are considered among others, as key cybersecurity requirements for the adoption of any new IoT technology, especially UAVs [73, 96, 97, 110]. A critical cybersecurity requirement of IoD is to apply appropriate cybersecurity mechanisms to ensure compliance with the CIA triad. Other important cybersecurity

requirements are Authenticity, Non-Repudiation, Authorization, Forward Secrecy, and Backward Secrecy [80, 87, 107].

A novel comprehensive taxonomy of cybersecurity attacks against IoD systems is provided in Tables ST3, ST4, ST5, and ST6 in Appendix C available in the electronic supplementary material. Each table presents the attacks according to the affected layer of the IoD system, namely software, hardware, and network/communication (including GPS signals) layer. In addition, a column specifies whether the attack is unique to IoD environment. The following subsections describe the most advanced of the attacks that affect each layer while the tables include all attacks per layer along with the affected cybersecurity principal based on the CIA triad. To the best of the authors' knowledge, there is no similar categorization of IoD cybersecurity threats in the literature.

4.2 Software Cybersecurity Issues

Similar to other types of software, UAV software is susceptible to several threats. Most of these threats are encountered in all types of software while others are specifically designed for UAV systems.

Malware: Malware is defined as software that is developed to cause disruption to a computer, server, network or other components of a system. A malware attack is realized when an attacker executes the malware in a target system such as a GCS with the aim of performing unauthorized tasks.

Database Attacks: In Wireless Sensor Networks (WSNs) and IoT-based communication environments, there are attacks that target database systems that are located on the cloud. This type of attacks could result in the unauthorized disclosure of information. Well-known examples of database attacks include **Cross-Site Scripting (XSS)** and **Cross-Site Request Forgery (CSRF)**.

Skyjack: This attack concerns the hijacking of the UAV during the flight operation. The sky-jacking malware is installed on the targeted UAV, thus providing the attacker the ability to identify wireless networks that are located in the proximity of the UAV. Subsequently, the pilot of the compromised UAV is disconnected, resulting in the loss of control. Subsequently, the UAV connects to the attacker's network in order to steal the target device.

Maldrone: Maldrone is defined as a generalized software which operates as a backdoor, and it leverages TCP ports by acting as a proxy between the flight controller of the target UAV and the sensor communication. Maldrone expects a TCP connection and once the connection is established, the attacker is able to communicate with the software and tamper with the sensors. Consequently, Maldrone provides the attacker with the ability to steal the target UAV.

Vulnerabilities in Operating Systems of UAVs: Despite the use of UAVs in a variety of domains, the existing operating systems and firmware lack basic cybersecurity features such as encryption. Furthermore, most UAV software (usually programmed in C or C++) have vulnerabilities which could be exploited leading to minor (e.g., flight disruption) or major consequences (e.g., theft, UAV crash).

PX4 and Ardupilot Software Bugs: PX4 is a well-known open-source flight control system that is used in UAVs as well as other unmanned vehicles. Ardupilot is an open-source software suite for autopilots of unmanned vehicles. Ardupilot operates on a variety of different hardware, thus supporting multiple types of UAVs including among others air, ground and underwater UAVs. Wang et al. conduct an extensive analysis concerning PX4 and Ardupilot. In particular, the authors analysed 569 bugs of these autopilot software and identified different types of UAV-specific bugs.

SQL Injection: SQL Injection is defined as an attack aiming at breaching SQL databases. Attackers try to execute malicious SQL queries with the aim of exploiting the vulnerabilities of the target database resulting in the injection of malicious commands. In case the attack is successful, the attackers are able to retrieve confidential data, alter the stored data and perform remote command

execution. UAVs that store their data (e.g., surveillance footage) on the cloud, could be targeted by this type of attack.

4.3 Hardware Cybersecurity Issues

Considering that UAVs are **Cyber-Physical Systems (CPSs)**, they are exposed to several cybersecurity risks that target hardware components.

Physical Capturing of WSN/IoT Devices / Tampering attack: Given that UAVs are physical devices, they carry the risk of physical capturing is possible by a physical adversary. The captured devices are inspected by the adversary who could use sensitive information that is stored in the UAV. Secret keys, media content and coordinates are some of the sensitive data that could be stored on the captured UAV.

Battery Depletion: Attacks consume additional battery power that decreases to a critical level or even to zero. The attack can occur in different states of the UAV, including hovering, moving, taking off/landing, in an on/off state during battery charging, in a standby state and in a completely off state. The rapid and premature draining of battery power has the consequence of the UAV returning to the base (home location) for charging, before the completion of the mission or even the UAV crashing.

4.4 Network and Communication Cybersecurity Issues

Communication among UAVs and GCSs is realized over an unsecured wireless channel. Furthermore, some communication protocols such as MAVLink are known to be prone to cyber-attacks.

Eavesdropping: Eavesdropping is also known as a sniffing or snooping attack. Eavesdropping concerns the exploitation of unsecured network channels to eavesdrop on the exchanged information among at least two communicating parties. An example of such communication which could be targeted in an IoD system is the exchange of messages between the GCS and the UAV.

Traffic Analysis: Traffic Analysis is similar to eavesdropping in terms of intercepting the exchanged messages during a communication. Nevertheless, in this case, the attacker captures the exchanged information and further examines their content. The attacker aims at identifying useful information regarding the communication between the GSC and the UAV. Such information may include but is not limited to the frequency of MAVLink communication, and the size of MAVLink packets.

Impersonation/Infiltration Attack: In impersonation attacks (also known as identity spoofing), the attacker exploits the IDs of legitimate users in order to masquerade as a legitimate user in the IoD network. Therefore, the attack is granted access to network resources. The MAVLink protocol is susceptible to impersonation attacks since uses the System IDs to identify the drone which sends or is expected to receive the messages. The ID is transmitted unencrypted within the MAVLink header. Consequently, an attack could easily intercept the transmitted message and steal the ID.

Hacking: Similar to software, hacking is considered a major cyber threat against the IoD environment. In case any device of the IoD system is susceptible to threat, the attacker is able to exploit them could lead to other threats concerning the rest of the devices.

Signal Tapping: Signal Tapping attacks are a type of passive hijacking attack. These attacks rely on the interception of transmitted data across the network channels in a real-time manner. Wireshark¹² is one of the most well-known solutions that are used to capture transmitted data.

Data Fabrication/Message Forgery: Data fabrication attacks concern the fabrication of fake information by unauthorized users. In order to successfully fabricate fake messages and send them

¹²<https://www.wireshark.org/>

to the target node (e.g., UAV, GCS), it is required to know the details of the communication protocol that is used by the GCS and the target UAV (e.g., MAVLink).

GPS Spoofing Attack: GPS Spoofing is considered one of the most common attacks against UAVs. The attacker generates fake GPS signals and transmits them to the target UAV, thus changing its direction. Initially, the attacker blocks the communication between the UAV and the GCS and proceeds with the transmission of fake signals.

Data Injection Attack: Data Injection attacks are categorized into two major categories, namely False/Fake Data Injection Attack and Generic False Data Injection Attack. The first category refers to the case where the attacker modifies the UAV's direction state estimation by tampering with the respective measurement in a manner that the modification is not detected by a bad measurement detector. With regard to the Generic False Data Injection Attack category, the attacker modifies the UAV's position estimation value within a certain limit.

Reduction Attack: Attackers modify the UAV distance measurement data by setting a smaller value so the UAV appears to be closer. Subsequently, the data is sent to the UAV.

Acoustic Attack: In acoustic attacks, the attacker leverages a hostile UAV including an acoustic asset that supports the generation of sound which differs from the targeted UAV's gyroscope resonant frequency. Consequently, the acoustic position control algorithm of the targeted UAV is affected.

Byzantine Attack: Byzantine attacks could be considered as a combination of different attacks. The attackers create routing loops, deliberately transmit packets across suboptimal paths, or attack availability by selecting specific packets that are dropped. The consequences of these actions include the perturbation as well as the degradation of routing services

Blackhole Attack: The attacker deceives the users that there is a new route for the transmitted messages. The attacker leverages forged control packets in order to be included in the network route. In case the transmitted messages choose to traverse a path that includes the malicious route, the attacker is then able to discard them instead of forwarding them to the next node.

Route Injection: The attacker attempts to inject additional hops in the existing route with the aim of redirecting the traffic to a monitored destination. Subsequently, the attacker could analyse and modify the information before it reaches the destination node.

DNS Cache Poisoning Attack: This attack aims at exploiting DNS server vulnerabilities to divert the traffic to a malicious server instead of the legitimate one. The attacker alters the DNS cache to resolve the DNS request to a fake website. Such attacks could lead to various risks including malware infections and data theft.

Wormhole Attack: Wormhole attacks require the collaboration of two attackers. One attacker is responsible for recording the packets at a specific location and forwarding them to the second attacker. Subsequently, the second attacker either analyses or completely drops the received packets.

Apart from the various cybersecurity techniques, anti-drone (also known as counter drone) technologies are introduced as an effective approach toward the defence against UAV incidents such as terrorism attacks or flight in restricted airspace [20, 84]. Anti-drone systems enable not only the detection of malicious UAVs but also the neutralization of the target. The majority of anti-drone approaches leverage military assets in order to eliminate the target UAV which makes the application of such techniques with regard to civilian application [84]. An example is **Radio Frequency (RF) jamming** that is used in order to disable the target drone control channel [104]. While the use of RF jamming is applicable in the military domain, it poses several risks when applied in non-military applications areas. The use of RF jamming malicious UAVs could result in temporal paralysis of wireless network nodes (e.g., WSN). Nevertheless, there are anti-drone systems which do not use military components (e.g., weapons) and are applicable in non-military application areas such as civil protection. The design as well as the implementation of anti-drone systems have to

meet some specific requirements. Park et al. [84] provide a comprehensive description of these requirements considering real UAV cybersecurity incidents such as terrorism.

4.5 Operational and Data-Centric Security Threats in IoD Systems

The IoD paradigm leverages UAVs to gather, relay, and process data in highly dynamic and often hazardous environments, where traditional cybersecurity strategies fall short due to unique operational demands and vulnerabilities. Specifically, IoD deployments necessitate robust, low-latency communications, real-time telemetry, continuous sensor fusion, and high-throughput video streaming, which collectively expose distinct vulnerabilities not adequately addressed by conventional security frameworks for UAVs or traditional IoT systems [28, 75, 108]. Due to space limitations this section is presented in the Appendix D.

4.6 Ransomware and Denial-of-Service (DoS) Attacks in IoD

Ransomware and DoS attacks represent two of the most disruptive and high-impact threats facing IoD environments. These attacks can compromise flight-control systems, overwhelm communication links, and jeopardize mission-critical operations, particularly in scenarios involving emergency response, critical infrastructure monitoring, or military reconnaissance. Given their potential to cause widespread disruption and financial damage, the study of these attack types and their countermeasures has become central to IoD cybersecurity research. A more extensive analysis, including detailed attack taxonomies and mitigation approaches, is presented in Annex E (e-pub only) due to space limitations.

4.7 Cross-layer Impact of Cyber-security Threats

Several studies in the literature demonstrate that a single vulnerability propagate across multiple architectural layers within an IoD deployment [10, 19, 83, 112]. Ameer et al. [19] demonstrated that when UAVs form a CHORD-based overlay the integrity of the finger-table directly conditions application-layer lookup success and, at the same time, exposes the lower A2A control links to extra signaling traffic, creating an inadvertent denial-of-service surface.

In particular, authors propose a UAV-assisted P2P-enabled VANET solution which includes a DQN-optimized swarm of UAV relays whose twin control knobs are (i) inter-UAV connectivity degree and (ii) residual energy level, both of which must stay above threshold to keep lookup latency low and success rate high [19]. Considering that these two parameters depend on lower-layer phenomena—RF interference, queue back-pressure, routing-table consistency, a single low-level assault (e.g., GPS spoofing that forces detours, or a battery-exhaustion attack on one relay) can trigger a domino effect: broken P2P overlay links reduce replica diversity, which in turn inflates application-layer retries and ultimately starves time-critical vehicular services.

Yerden et al. [112] introduced a threat modeling framework (xT-STRIDE) for UAV/IoD systems that examines security at each layer of a multi-layered drone architecture. In particular, they define a reference IoD architecture (covering embedded hardware, communication links, and software stack) and systematically analyse threats to each component, along with countermeasures in the corresponding trusted layer. By incorporating the drone's communication and onboard computing architecture into the model, the study demonstrates how cross-layer threats (e.g., an exploit in a drone's firmware affecting network behavior) can be identified and mitigated during the design phase.

Furthermore, Osmani and Schulz [83] examined the layered architecture of UAV avionics (e.g., computing, control, communication, sensors) and associated failure modes. The authors observed that the tightly coupled multi-layer system architecture of drones can induce cascading failure effects – a fault in one component or layer (e.g., a sensor or communication module) may compromise the

entire UAV system. The authors reviewed how interactions between electronic, mechanical, and software layers can amplify vulnerabilities, and stress the need for cross-disciplinary safeguards in drone (and IoD) design.

Another notable work by Aldossary et al. [10] which presents a unified IDS framework for the IoD that leverages a cross-layer convolutional attention network to monitor both drone-to-drone and drone-to-base station traffic. The authors noted that IoD is a multi-layered network architecture susceptible to data breaches, DDoS, GPS spoofing, and other attacks across its layers. Their proposed IDS (CLCAN) fuses multi-layer features to detect complex cyber threats in real time, significantly improving detection accuracy and closing a security gap in IoD communications.

To clarify these vertical interdependencies, Table ST8 in Appendix F in the electronic supplementary material presents information concerning effects of each attack on the subsequent IoD layers. Each cell represents a lower layer attack, and the net negative effect at a higher layer.

5 IoD Security Mechanisms

Given the vulnerable nature of IoD, it is critical to address key cybersecurity requirements such as confidentiality, integrity, and non-repudiation. There is considerable research toward the proposal of cybersecurity techniques that UAVs could implement to meet cybersecurity requirements. Most IoT devices and especially UAVs are designed with lacking even fundamental cybersecurity protection (e.g., authentication mechanism) [88]. Furthermore, the communication established between UAVs within the IoD network is over insecure channels (e.g., mainly wireless network and Bluetooth) as well as navigational signals such as GPS or other satellite-based navigation system (e.g., **Global Navigation Satellite Systems (GNSS)** [93]). The cybersecurity issues affect mostly commercial UAVs which operate in civilian areas, while military UAVs are considered more secure against various cyber-attacks [21, 40, 71, 103]. Nevertheless, skilled attackers could successfully compromise military UAVs. A notable incident of a compromised military drone is the CIA Lockheed Martin RQ-170 Sentinel US spy drone which was captured by Iranian forces near the city of Kashmar in December 2011 by forcing it to shift into autopilot mode [1]. Consequently, in order to enhance the protection of IoD various cybersecurity and privacy approaches are proposed in the literature.

A notable example of lightweight and proactive security is presented by de Melo et al. [34]. In their work, the authors proposed a decentralized identity and location validation scheme that combines a public-key based authentication mechanism with a movement plausibility check specifically designed for UAV networks, achieving effective location validation and robust identity authentication through decentralized voting and mobility-pattern checks, while keeping resource overhead minimal.

Beyond decentralized schemes, access control protocols are introduced as a critical cybersecurity technique which facilitates the privacy of the data [77]. Access control is defined as a cybersecurity scheme which controls the view, use and access rights of assets. Given the power limitations of UAVs access control protocols are considered more suitable as they avoid high power consumption, thus extending the operating time of the UAV [25].

Another cybersecurity technique that is constantly gaining more research interest is the deployment of **Intrusion Detection Systems (IDS)** in order to detect malicious behavior in network traffic [20, 87]. In particular, an IDS monitors the incoming as well as the outgoing network traffic of FANET and analyses the data in order to detect possible anomalies which might indicate malicious behavior. The network traffic of FANET regards communication between UAVs (e.g., drone swarms) or communication between UAVs and terrestrial equipment (e.g., GCS).

FANETs are characterized by distinct differences from other types of Ad-Hoc networks such as MANETs and VANETs in terms of various aspects. In particular, FANETs have different abilities which include among others, mobility, node density, operational environment and routing protocols.

Table 2. Comparison of MANET, VANET, and FANET

Characteristic	MANET	VANET	FANET
Node speed	Lower (6 km/h)	Medium to high (Average 20–130 km/h)	Low to high (6–460 km/h)
Node Density	Low	VANETs have higher node density as they operate at ground level with vehicles that are closer together, High	FANETs usually operate with lower node density at higher altitudes, Very Low
Degree of mobility	Consistent, 2D, Random trajectories, Low	Consistent, 2D, Random trajectories, High	Free, 3D, Either random or predefined trajectories, Very high
Propagation model	On the ground	On the ground	In the air
Frequency band	30 GHz –5 GHz	5.9 GHz	UAV-2-UAV-5GHz UAV-2-G-2.4 GHz
Topology	Ad-hoc, Random	Star with roadside infrastructure and Ad-hoc among Vehicles	Star and Mesh (with Base Station), Ad-hoc (between UAVs)
Topology change	Dynamic, Unpredictable	Linear movement, Fast	Stationary, Slow and Fast
Wireless technology	IEEE 802.11a/b/g/n, IEEE 802.16	IEEE 802.11p	IEEE 802.11a/b/g/ac/ax/s/n/p
Line of sight	Not available	Low in urban areas	High
Computational process	Limited	High	High
Energy constraints	Medium	Low	High (15–30 minutes), Medium (up to 5 hours)
Localization	GPS	GPS/AGPS (Assisted Global Positioning System)	GPS/AGPS
Operational Environment	Urban or semi-urban environments for communication between portable devices	Urban or semi-urban environments for communication between vehicles	Deployed in remote or inaccessible areas for tasks like monitoring and surveillance

Furthermore, FANETs differ from WSNs (Wireless Sensor Networks). While both FANETs and WSNs are types of wireless networks, they have distinct differences and are designed for different applications. FANET nodes are highly mobile with three-dimensional movement, which presents unique challenges in network stability [86]. On the other hand, WSN nodes may be mobile or immobile, but even mobile sensors have limited movement compared to FANET nodes [101]. Concerning the application domains, FANETs are used in applications that require aerial mobility, such as disaster management, military operations, and traffic monitoring [86]. WSNs are deployed for environmental monitoring, health care, and industrial automation, where sensing and data collection are essential [101]. Consequently, security mechanisms that monitor the network (e.g., IDS) need to be adapted accordingly in order to address the unique challenges of FANETs. Table 2 presents a detailed comparison between MANET, VANET, and FANET networks.

Gupta et al. [36] discussed the details of IDS approaches that are proposed for WSNs. Considering that IoD is in fact a specialized version of IoT, some proposed cybersecurity approaches concerning IoT might also be applicable to UAVs. A survey of IDS systems for IoT environments is provided in Zarpelão et al. [113]. The authors described the different trends, open issues and future research directions in IoT communications. Furthermore, the authors divided the IDS according to distinct features. Another survey of IDS systems for the IoT environment is provided in Khan and Herrmann [61], in which the authors discussed the details of IDS for the MANETs, WSNs, and CPSs. Furthermore, the authors provided the advantages and disadvantages of each considered technique.

5.1 Emerging Security Solutions in IoD

Recent research highlights the increasing role of advanced methods such as AI- and blockchain-based approaches in addressing evolving IoD cybersecurity challenges. These developments mark a shift from reactive defences toward proactive and adaptive mechanisms, where intelligent detection, predictive analytics, and decentralized trust frameworks provide more robust protection. Together, they represent a critical step toward securing large-scale, heterogeneous, and mission-critical IoD ecosystems. A detailed discussion of these emerging security solutions is presented in Annex G (e-pub only) due to space limitations.

5.2 Threat-Modeling

The analysis of recent solutions presented in previous sections indicates that an important aspect of cybersecurity is the implementation of proactive measures enabling the protection from cyber-attacks before they occur while reactive cybersecurity measures concern the mechanisms that are utilized in order to respond to a cybersecurity incident. Among other proactive approaches in the literature, threat modeling is introduced as an effective proactive measure to enhance the cybersecurity of a system [27].

Threat modeling has various definitions in the literature [107]. A generic definition is provided by Ling et al. [68] where threat modeling is defined as a solution which enables the modeling of various cybersecurity threats that could affect the system and are usually used to run simulations. A widely-accepted definition is provided by Uzunov and Fernandez [102]. According to the authors, “threat modeling is a process that can be used to analyse potential attacks or threats, and can also be supported by threat libraries or attack taxonomies”. Another acceptable definition is provided by Bedi et al. [23] which defines threat modeling as a method that “provides a structured way to secure software design, which involves understanding an adversary’s goal in attacking a system based on system’s assets of interest”. Baquero et al. [22] provided a definition of threat modeling in terms of application development.

Apart from assessing the threats and risks of a system, threat models can also be leveraged toward system evaluation. Dhillon [37] defined threat modeling as “the architecture of the system is represented and analysed, potential cybersecurity threats are identified, and appropriate mitigation techniques are selected”. Dolev and Yao [38] define threat modeling as a systematic process that aims at achieving three specific goals:

- (1) Identify the potential attackers that could target the system.
- (2) Identify both cybersecurity vulnerabilities as well as threats within the system or sub-system component that could be used as attack paths.
- (3) Provide crucial information that could be utilized to enhance the cybersecurity of the target system or sub-system against possible attacks and facilitate the development of improved cybersecurity requirements.

While the definition of threat modeling has many variations, the overall scope of this approach is clear. Threat modeling helps to identify cybersecurity threats that may affect the system by a proper examination of the system from an adversary’s point of view. Since the threats are identified during the design process, it facilitates the reduction of the cost toward the implementation of appropriate measures to achieve high standards of cybersecurity [46]. Furthermore, threat modeling facilitates the design of respective mitigation actions in order to address the identified threats.

5.3 Analysis of IoD Threat Models

Given the importance of proactive cybersecurity measures, the use of threat modeling is continuously increasing in application development as well as in system evaluation [107]. During the last years, many threat models as well as modeling methodologies have been proposed. Dolev Yao threat model [27, 38, 55, 110] and the more recent Canetti and Krawczyk threat model (CK-adversary model) [27, 30, 55, 110] are two of the most prevalent threat models that are used in most research articles in the literature. Among the most popular approaches are the following: (i) STRIDE modeling, (ii) **Process for Attack Simulation and Threat Analysis (PASTA)**, (iii) Trike modeling, (iv) **Visual, Agile, and Simple Threat modeling (VAST)**, and (v) OCTAVE modeling [43]. Many proposed cybersecurity approaches found in the literature leverage threat models in order to either enhance the cybersecurity capabilities of the proposed solution or to evaluate the system, thus, facilitating the implementation of the proposed solution.

Threat models are utilized in various domains in order to facilitate and enhance system protection. In particular, many researchers leverage threat models in conjunction with other well-established approaches such as blockchain solutions. To facilitate the study of the various threat models in the literature, the published articles are categorized as either works that implement threat models as part of a proposed solution or works that propose novel threat models.

5.3.1 Solutions Utilizing Threat Models. Dolev Yao threat model is a widely accepted threat model focused on cryptographic tools. The threat model considers the following assumptions [110]:

- (1) Information is exchanged over an insecure channel.
- (2) The attacker is able to selectively intercept the messages that are transmitted across the channels.
- (3) The adversary could masquerade as any legitimate entity node in the network.
- (4) The attacker is able to exchange messages with any other legitimate nodes by masquerading as one of them.

According to the threat model, the attacker is considered to have total control of the communication channel including all the messages that are exchanged between the nodes. Nevertheless, there are some restrictions concerning the attacker's capabilities:

- The adversary does not have the means to infer a randomly generated number from a large space.
- The attacker is not able to decrypt a ciphertext without the acquisition of the appropriate decryption (private) key.
- The attacker is not able to infer the private keys from the corresponding public keys.

The Canetti and Krawczyk threat model [30] shares all the features of the Dolev Yao threat model, while it considers also providing the attacker with the ability to exploit the secret values including private keys stored in the memory space of the legitimate nodes by performing power analysis against the target system [110].

Pundir et al. [87] discussed the various cybersecurity requirements and threats affecting WSNs and IoT-based systems and describe a threat model that can enhance cybersecurity within this environment. The authors define WSNs as “the assemblage of homogeneous and heterogeneous resource-constrained sensing devices which sense the environment's physical phenomenon and transmit the information to the sink node (base station) via different modes of communication”. An important advantage of WSNs is the ability to operate and provide important results from unattended geographical locations. Therefore, WSN is used in a variety of critical applications among which are border surveillance, industrial monitoring, business applications and healthcare monitoring [87]. In terms of their relationship, WSNs and IoD exhibit fundamental similarities in their operational characteristics. Both involve distributed, resource-constrained nodes equipped with sensing capabilities, tasked with collecting, processing, and transmitting data back to centralized or distributed control points. UAVs essentially function as mobile, aerial nodes within an IoD network, often operating autonomously in remote, unattended, or hostile environments. Consequently, cybersecurity threats and mitigation strategies developed for WSNs, particularly those concerning secure communication, resource limitations, and unattended operation, are highly relevant and transferable to IoD systems. In addition, IoD scenarios often involve UAV missions such as border surveillance, environmental monitoring, industrial inspection, and emergency response, which are directly analogous to the critical applications identified for WSNs. Therefore, cybersecurity frameworks and threat models originating in WSN and IoT-based systems provide foundational insights and methodologies that are inherently beneficial and applicable to the distinct cybersecurity challenges of IoD and UAV deployments.

Considering the ability of WSNs (e.g., air pollution monitoring, smart health monitoring, smart traffic management), WSNs are often targeted by attackers. Pundir et al. [87] argue that the Dolev-Yao threat model can be utilized in order to enhance the cybersecurity of WSNs communications. According to the model, as described by the authors, the communication between the nodes is performed over an insecure channel. The attacker A has the following capabilities:

- Alter, delete or insert data during the communication (affecting the integrity of data).
- Physically capture sensor/IoT sensors, thus allowing the extraction of important information from their memory [76, 94].
- Clone new malicious nodes with different attack functionalities.

Upon a successful attack against the target system, the data packets the communication could be affected in terms of being lost, discarded, delayed or altered, thus hindering the communication between the sensor devices.

Bera et al. [25] proposed a novel access control protocol for battlefield surveillance in a drone-assisted IoT environment, called ACPBS-IoT. The authors utilized both the Dolev-Yao and the Canetti and Krawczyk's threat models to design the proposed access control protocol. Based on the DY model, an attacker A can delete, hijack or modify the exchanged information as well as insert harmful data during the communication between the drone DR_i and its associated Ground Station Server GSS_j . According to the CK threat model, attacker A has the means to compromise a session state and reveal the secret credentials including secret keys with the condition that they are available in the insecure memory of the DR_i . Attacker A can also intercept the exchanged messages that are transmitted over the public channel.

Xiong and Lagerström [107] conducted a comprehensive study on threat modeling by using systematic queries in widely used scientific databases. Initially, the authors identified 176 articles, while only 54 were selected out of them for further analysis assessment. The articles were divided into three distinct clusters: (i) articles contributing to threat modeling (C1), (ii) articles that utilize existing threat modeling approaches (C2), and (iii) articles describing approaches related to threat modeling (C3). The articles in each cluster have been analysed based on different criteria such as if the threat modeling approach is considered graphical or formal. According to Xiong and Lagerström [107], formal modeling is a method that leverages mathematical models while graphical modeling utilizes methods such as attack trees, attack graphs, or tables. According to the results, there is a small number of research articles concerning automatic threat modeling methods. Nevertheless, a valid argument is that due to the nature of the IoD environment and the system of UAV devices, automatic threat modeling is more efficient compared to manual approaches.

Karatas et al. [59] proposed a novel bi-objective location-allocation problem for UAVs that operate within a hostile environment. A threat model is adopted to model the possible threats originating from the **Named Area of Interest (NAI)** against UAS locations. The NAI is defined as an area that contains one or several threats that have to be identified and addressed by the UAV [59]. The threat model is based on the **Multinomial Logit (MNL)** discrete choice model [2]. In addition, many articles in the literature use Random utility models (notably MNL models), in terms of threat estimation and regarding the modeling of analytical models [59].

Almulhem [14] presented a study regarding threats affecting IoD networks. In order to enumerate the possible threats, the authors utilize the threat tree modeling approach. Due to the complexity of IoD networks as well as the diverse threats that target such systems, the authors propose a two-step approach to design and develop the threat tree. Initially, the tree is populated according to the IoD reference model [41] and is further refined by mapping the main nodes into the fundamental cybersecurity properties (i.e., Confidentiality, Integrity, Availability).

5.3.2 Novel Threat Models. While many articles are proposing cybersecurity techniques and methods for UAVs utilizing existing well-known threat models, the research for novel threat modeling approaches is continuously increasing. Many researchers propose novel threat modeling or threat assessment approaches concerning different application domains which include among others, healthcare [8], transportation systems [46, 91], android devices [79] and military [69, 84].

Gupta et al. [43] argued that ML or DL models could facilitate addressing the issues regarding the identification of similar or new threats. According to the authors, ML is a suitable solution due to the ability to learn hidden patterns using back-propagation to identify similar data analysis security threats. With regard to DL, apart from the ability to detect known or new threats, the feature extractions extraction process can be automated without requiring human intervention resulting in a more complete representation of data. In this regard, the authors propose an ML-based and DL-based **Secure Data Analytics (SDA)** architecture that enables the classification of either legitimate or malicious input data.

Salamh et al. [95] proposed a modified STRIDE threat model for **Drones as a Service (DaaS)** named DIREST-TMM as an acronym of DoS, Information disclosure, Repudiation, Escalation of privilege, Spoofing GPS protocol, and Tampering. STRIDE is a widely used software-centric threat modeling approach that was developed in the late 1990s by Loren Kohnfelder and Praerit Garg, two engineers who at the time were working at Microsoft [78]. The name STRIDE stands as the acronym for Spoofing, Tampering, Repudiation, Information Disclosure, Denial of Service, and Elevation of Privileges. The proposed DIREST-TMM threat model aims at enhancing five aspects of DaaS cybersecurity, which include confidentiality, integrity, availability, and safety [95]. In particular, the model is categorized in an ascending order considering cybersecurity risk level.

Concerning “low-slow-small” targets, a threat assessment method based on the coefficient of variation is proposed by Sun et al. [100]. In particular, the proposed method is a **Technique for Order Preference by Similarity to an Ideal Solution (TOPSIS)** threat degree ranking method based on the coefficient of variation. TOPSIS is a multi-criteria decision analysis method, that has been proposed by Ching-Lai Hwang and Yoon [52]. The proposed method leverages the coefficient of variation which is defined as a statistical index that is used for comparison and measurement of the variation degree regarding each observation value within a dataset, that describes the deviation degree of the measurements [100]. Therefore, the method can be implemented in order to determine the weight of each value by calculating the variability degree individually for every index. The authors argue that the threat degree of a UAV depends on four distinct factors. The distance between the UAV and the control centre, the height at which the UAV is flying, the flying speed, and the UAV’s intent to attack. In order to calculate the values of each of the aforementioned values, the authors define four respective mathematical formulas. Subsequently, weight factor once the weight of each value has been defined based on the coefficient of Variation, TOPSIS method is used to calculate the threat degree.

An important aspect of proactive cybersecurity measures concerning UAVs is the ability to detect abnormal behavior of a UAV that could indicate malicious intent. Despite the fact that many different surveillance technologies have been developed and deployed in critical areas such as airports to detect UAVs, they often lack the means to determine which of the detected UAVs exhibits abnormal behavior. Due to this issue, Liang et al. [67] leverage a Bayesian approach which enables the early detection of a UAV, threatening or abnormal behavior in a surveyed region.

Liu et al. [69] addressed the UAV air combat problem and particularly the air combat mission between the multiple UAVs and hostile multi-UAV. In this regard, the authors describe a multi-UAV air combat threat assessment which enables the assessment of the threat that a hostile UAV poses to a benign UAV. The overall threat of a hostile UAV to a benign UAV is calculated based on three values, namely angle threat, speed threat and distance threat.

While various proposed cybersecurity approaches leverage threat models which focus on specific domains and assets, there are approaches which utilize generic threat modeling approaches toward enhancing the security of the proposed solution. Aggarwal et al. [8] proposed a three-layered architecture which enables collecting, processing and transmitting medical data in real-time. In order to identify the threats that may target the architecture, the authors implement a threat model which analyses attacks targeting Confidentiality, Integrity and Availability. Furthermore, a threat model in order to enumerate the attacks that affect Android systems is proposed by Negi et al. [79]. In particular, the model depicts the attacks that target each layer of the Android architecture.

Similar to mobile devices operating on Android, UAVs are also considered mobile devices, thus being susceptible to similar threats such as posing the risk of being lost as a result of a crash or stolen. Therefore, the approach of modeling the potential threats based on the architecture layer could also be applicable in UAVs.

Threat modeling is an effective approach toward securing the cybersecurity of UAVs both in terms of the protection of the device as well as the protection of possible targets of a malicious drone (e.g., airports, military combat applications). In addition, threat modeling is considered useful concerning secure application development [3, 4] and system analysis and design [49, 92]. Despite the advantages of threat models, some researchers argue that the threat modeling approaches are complex, require much time, and are prone to errors [50, 91, 105]. Due to these issues, Ramazanzadeh et al. [91] proposed the **Automated Cybersecurity Assistant of Threat Models (ASATM)**. According to the authors, ASATM “enables the cybersecurity analyst to design, measure and evaluate different cybersecurity scenarios within the shortest period of time in a simple and fully automated manner by drawing on the basic cybersecurity model”. ASATM also provides the ability to simulate and assess any hardware or software component while also providing a variety of cybersecurity modes.

5.4 Balancing Security and Operational Efficiency in IoD Systems: Key Tradeoffs and Considerations

The integration of advanced cryptographic mechanisms, most notably blockchain and elliptic curve cryptography, has substantially reinforced security in UAV systems, particularly with respect to secure data storage, robust authentication, and the assurance of data integrity [39, 54]. Despite the various advantages, these cryptographic approaches are inherently computationally demanding, which poses significant challenges given the constrained processing capabilities and energy resources characteristic of UAVs. Consequently, the adoption of such techniques can lead to negative consequences including reduced flight endurance as well as diminished operational range [26, 56]. For instance, while blockchain-based frameworks deliver decentralized, tamper-evident security assurances, they also impose considerable computational and communication overheads due to the necessity of consensus algorithms and the continual maintenance of distributed ledgers [89].

Similarly, the implementation of AI-driven IDS can significantly enhance threat prediction and response capabilities within IoD networks [7, 16]. While the implementation of sophisticated ML algorithms onboard UAVs can significantly enhance their security capabilities, it imposes additional demands on computational and energy resources which could adversely impact latency-sensitive tasks, such as real-time data collection, collision avoidance, and mission-critical communications [5, 31]. In particular, DL methods, despite their high accuracy in anomaly detection, require substantial computational power and energy resources, raising concerns in terms of their practical feasibility for smaller or energy-constrained [72, 90].

Another important tradeoff involves increased communication overhead and the scalability of the network. Protocols designed for high security, such as robust authentication and frequent key exchanges, typically consume significant bandwidth. Consequently, these measures can decrease

overall network throughput, increase latency, and restrict the number of UAVs simultaneously supported within a deployment, thereby limiting IoD network scalability [32, 62]. In conclusion, finding the right balance between security and efficiency depends greatly on the context in which the system is deployed. In scenarios such as military reconnaissance or emergency response, security is often the primary priority, despite the increased computational and energy demands [21, 33]. On the other hand, for large-scale commercial or civilian applications of the IoD, where factors like prolonged mission duration, cost-effectiveness, and scalability are crucial, it often makes sense to pursue a more pragmatic balance. In these cases, operational efficiency may take precedence, provided that an acceptable level of security is still maintained [35, 65].

Therefore, decision-makers are encouraged to conduct comprehensive risk assessments and to align cybersecurity measures with the operational requirements, mission profiles, and resource constraints of their IoD deployments. Such targeted decision-making can ensure both strong cybersecurity and optimal performance across diverse IoD scenarios [35, 59].

6 Categorization and Evaluation of Threat Modeling and Assessment Approaches

There are various threat modeling approaches which are applicable to different domains including Android devices [79], UAVs [58], WSN and IoT [87]. Apart from the application domain, threat modeling approaches are also categorized based on different criteria.

Luo et al. [70] provide a novel classification of TARA approaches. In particular, authors classify the approaches as either model-based or formula-based methods. Approaches that fall under the former taxonomy, are defined as methods which implement various different models for the modeling and analysis of risks regarding the system by utilizing data flow diagrams, graphs, as well as tree models. On the other hand, formula-based methods use tables, texts, or mathematical formulas for threat analysis and risk assessment purposes. Each category is further divided into different sub-categories according to their distinct features. With regard to formal-based methods, they are further classified into three types according to their different concerns (i.e., asset based, vulnerability-based, and attacker-based).

- **Asset-based Methods:** This type is considered as the most common type of TARA approach concerning automotive applications. The asset-based approach initially identifies the asset that is targeted by an attack and subsequently identifies all possible attack paths and attack methods that could lead to the exploitation of the asset.
- **Vulnerability-based Methods:** Similar to asset-based, vulnerability-based approaches follow a “bottom-up” approach. Vulnerability-based methods initially identify a vulnerability in the system and subsequently analyse the possible consequences (e.g., vulnerabilities or other failures) which could of the identified vulnerability.
- **Attacker-based Methods:** Attacker-based method focuses on analysing attackers instead of the system. The method performs threat analysis and risk assessment considering the information regarding attackers that may target the system, attack paths that can be used, attack motivations, and the number of possessed resources. Consequently, threats can be modeled and analysed from their starting point.

With regard to model-based methods, the threat analysis process leverages various models, modeling and analysing the threats as well as risks utilizing graphs, data flow diagrams, and tree models. Furthermore, these methods are more complex, thus making them more difficult to implement and understand [70]. Similar to formula-based, model-based methods are further classified as either graph-based or tree-based.

- **Graph-based Methods:** Graph-based methods describe the different threats against the system as interconnected nodes and directional edges, known as attack graphs [70, 91].

Table 3. Classifications of Threat Models in the Literature

Year	Reference	Classification
2019	[107]	Manual/Automatic and Formal/Graphical” methods
2020	[46]	Attack-Centric, Assets-Centric, Vulnerability and Threat-Centric, Software-Centric, Attack Trees
2021	[70]	Model-based or Formula-based methods
2021	[68]	Classification based on different information sources
2022	[91]	Manual/Automatic and Formal/Graphical” methods

Due to the ability to present each node’s direct quantitative relationship in a mathematical manner, graph-based methods are considered to expedite the system’s quantitative threat analysis [70].

- **Tree-based Methods:** Tree-based methods illustrate the association among the nodes in a hierarchical manner. The attack tree model leverages a tree as a structure to model the threats that may target the system, along with the relevant attack paths. Similar to model-based, formula-based approaches are further divided into three types that are characterized by different features.

Xiong and Lagerström [107] presented a systematic literature review of threat modeling. The authors study a wide range of different articles concerning threat modeling and classify them into two main categories, namely “manual/automatic” methods and “formal/graphical” methods. Similarly, authors Ramazanzadeh et al. [91] classified threat modeling methods as manual/automatic methods and formal/graphical methods. Furthermore, the authors argue that most studies have focused on the implementation of a manual threat model. Therefore, there is a need for studies which focus on automated threat modeling since manual methods introduce critical challenges such as complexity and increased chance of human error.

A different classification is provided by Hamad and Prevelakis [46] where threat modeling methods are classified into five different categories. The authors argue that threat modeling is implemented by independently utilizing one of the categories.

- **Attacker-Centric:** Attack-Centric threat models leverage profiles of attackers’ characteristics in terms of their anticipated goals, skills, and motivations. The main concept of these threat models is that these profiles could provide sufficient information for the system administrators to be able to implement more effective mitigation to defend against possible cyber-attacks.
- **Assets-Centric:** Threat models of this category rely on profiling assets that pose a greater risk of being attacked by the attackers as well as identifying the vulnerabilities of these assets. An asset is defined as anything that is considered valuable in the system [46].
- **Vulnerability and Threat-Centric:** This type of threat models focuses on the risky vulnerabilities that are more likely to be exploited by the attackers to implement appropriate mitigation.
- **Software-Centric:** This is also category is also referred to as design-centric. Software-Centric is a special case of the Assets-Centric method given that this category focuses on software components which are a type of asset. The aim is at ensuring the cybersecurity of the system during the software’s design phase by detecting threats which may be exploited by an attacker. A widely known threat model that follows the Software-Centric approach is the STRIDE threat model [98].
- **Attack Trees:** Attack trees or tree-based methods, are defined similarly to [70].

A comparison of the different proposed approaches in the literature is presented in Table 3.

This work presents a comprehensive study regarding a variety of threat models, categorizing and evaluating them with respect to their applicability to the IoD domain. While all categorizations are considered important and provide different advantages, this work argues that the most critical categorization is the distinction between manual and automatic threat modeling approaches. An important characteristic of UAV devices is the fact that they are portable. Therefore, during their operation, the devices could connect to different untrusted networks.

According to Javaid et al. [58], it is significantly important to secure these channels, since they transmit critical information. The diversity of different channel types is considered another important issue of UAV systems. Different channel types of a UAVNet include a range of communication, different power consumption requirements, different data flow types, as well as confidentiality and integrity requirements.

Due to the limitations of threat modeling methods which follow a manual approach, there is a need to have a secure system which is able to learn the patterns of the existing threats and identify behaviors within the system. Due to their mathematical nature, formula-based methods are a suitable approach concerning automatic threat modeling. Formula-based methods can be utilized by ML algorithms in order to facilitate the automatic threat modeling of a UAV system based on various factors (e.g., device type). On the other hand, model-based methods follow a different approach, making them more suitable toward manual threat modeling.

Initially, the threat models were categorized as manual, automatic, or manual/automatic according to the features provided by each model. Subsequently, the models that have been categorized as either automatic or manual/automatic, are further evaluated to identify features that make them suitable for IoD systems. The results of the evaluation of the different threat models in terms of their applicability to IoD, are presented in Table ST11 in Appendix H in the electronic supplementary material.

6.1 Evaluation of Threat Models

This section presents an analytical evaluation of threat modeling methodologies relevant to IoD environments, aiming at addressing RQ3 and RQ4 of the research methodology. Specifically, the evaluation presented in this section provides valuable insights into each methodology's strengths and limitations, as well as their applicability to the IoD domain. Consequently, this assessment aims at guiding practitioners and researchers toward either selecting or adapting suitable threat modeling approaches tailored explicitly for IoD cybersecurity scenarios.

EVITA: "EVITA includes a hardware component which is defined as an extension of vehicular hardware. The architecture applies three distinct versions of dedicated **hardware security modules (HSM)**, which are hardware devices that enable the secure and efficient implementation of cryptographic operations and the secure operation of dedicated security mechanisms.

The EVITA Hardware Security Module Light Version (EVITA HSM Light Version) is intended to integrate and protect ECUs, sensors and actuators that provide or process security-critical information. The specific version could be integrated with UAVs as an additional security component. Nevertheless, the energy consumption cost is not mentioned in the article. Therefore, since UAVs are energy-constrained devices, the use of additional equipment which consumes the battery energy should be avoided."

HEAVENS: HEAVENS Security Model analyses threats based on Microsoft's STRIDE. The proposed method can be considered as generic. The risk assessment consists of three steps which could be applicable to both UGVs and UAVs.

SHIELD: "SHIELD is a methodology for assessing **security, privacy, and dependability (SPD)** of embedded systems and part of a European collaboration of the same name. SHIELD is defined as a multimetric approach used to evaluate the system's level of SPD. The main target of this method

is to evaluate multiple system configurations and select those that meet or achieve established requirements. The proposed method can be considered generic, thus being able to adapt to the IoD environment. Nevertheless, SHIELD could be problematic.”

TVRA: “Within ETSI a **Threat Vulnerability and Risk Analysis (TVRA)** is used to identify risk to the system based upon the product of the likelihood of an attack as well as the impact that such an attack. The TVRA models are utilized by a system consisting of assets which may be physical, human or logical. The output of the TVRA is a quantified measure of the risks to the assets and a set of detailed security countermeasures that will minimize that risk.

Identification of the **Target of Evaluation (TOE)** resulting in a high-level description of the main assets of the TOE and the TOE environment and a specification of the goal, purpose and scope of the TVRA.

US²: Driving Automation Levels (DAL) defines the driving tasks of autonomous vehicles which are automated, and the human activities in AVs. The automated driving tasks can be considered equivalent to UAV mission flights.

FMVEA: Given that UAVs are considered Cyber Physical Systems, this method is applicable to UAVs and IoD devices.

VeRA: For the Attack Probability P, the method considers three levels of attacker’s knowledge K and three levels of Equipment E. This is relevant to UAVs since an attacker may need special equipment for attacks such as GPS jamming or spoofing.

SAM: The model is designed specifically for the automotive industry.

Bayesian Stackelberg Game: The model depends heavily on mathematical formulas. Therefore, it can be adapted to different domains such as IoD systems.

VAST: This could be helpful during the development of a custom script or application for the UAV, in order to identify potential vulnerabilities during the development process.

Markov Chain: The authors propose an attack evaluation system based on the attack tree model and Markov chain to assess the probability of compromising the **Controller Area Network (CAN)** and the steady state of CAN system in the presence of these attacks. Given that there is the OpenCyphal¹³ (formerly **Uncomplicated Application-level Vehicular Computing and Networking - UAVCAN**) is a lightweight protocol, the proposed method can be applicable for UAVs as well.

GTS (Graph Transformation System): The model is designed specifically for the automotive industry. Too complex.

Bayesian Network: The UAV-related events which are described in the article, are applicable to the IoD field as well. The authors propose a quantitative evaluation method based on the Bayes net for the UV risk without specifying the type of the UAV (e.g., UGV, UAV). Therefore, the proposed method can be considered as generic. The addressed issues could concern both UGVs and UAVs.

UML-based Model: First, the authors formalize a system, a case of cyber-physical systems, using UML class and activity diagrams. Further, the authors use UML to develop a meta-language for autonomous vehicle systems, cyber attacks, and cyber countermeasures. The framework instantiates the dependent application diagrams for the domain application of autonomous vehicles, searches for the existing attack surfaces; and then generates the possible attacks that might exploit the found vulnerabilities/weaknesses.

Furthermore, the proposed framework generates the proper Java code for the composition of countermeasures, attacks, and smart vehicle models. Given that UAVs are considered as Cyber-Physical Systems, this method is applicable to UAVs and IoD devices.”

¹³<https://github.com/OpenCyphal/pycyphal>

Attack Tree Analysis (ATA): Due to its complicated nature, ATA does not fit the architecture of IoD devices.

RISKEE (Risk Tree): RISKEE is a generic threat model. According to Krisper et al. [64], RISKEE can be embedded into the development process already very early on, at the architectural phase or at the design phase and can be refined during development as well as later on during runtime.

CVSS: This could be combined with the **Software (SW)** Vulnerability Analysis to determine the severity of an identified vulnerability.

Software Vulnerability Analysis: SW Vulnerability Analysis could facilitate the identification of possible vulnerabilities in the case where the user uses open-source software such as flight controllers or during the development of a custom script for the UAV.

6.2 Comparative Analysis of Threat Modeling Frameworks

To provide additional clarity and facilitate a comprehensive understanding, this subsection introduces a comparative analysis of prominent threat modeling frameworks frequently employed in IoD environments. This comparison explicitly outlines each framework's core principles, strengths, limitations, and relevance to UAV and IoD networks. Furthermore, recent advancements in 5G network slicing for UAVs introduce distinct cybersecurity challenges, notably cross-slice attacks and breaches of resource isolation due to multi-tenant architectures [29]. Due to space limitations, further elaboration is presented in Appendix H.1 of the electronic supplementary material.

7 Conclusions and Future Research

This survey provides an extensive analysis of cybersecurity issues and proactive countermeasures pertaining to UAVs and the broader IoD ecosystem. Despite the increasing deployment of UAVs across governmental, commercial, and critical infrastructure domains, fundamental cybersecurity remains underdeveloped in most commercial systems. The research identified that UAVs and IoD devices are vulnerable to a wide spectrum of cyber threats, with exploitation possible even using readily available equipment such as WiFi Pineapple devices.^{14,15} Autopilot software and communication protocols, including widely used solutions like ArduPilot and MAVLink, remain susceptible to attack. At the same time, ongoing development efforts are attempting to address these issues by embedding more robust cybersecurity features.

A persistent challenge for safeguarding IoD devices lies in their inherent resource constraints. Advanced cybersecurity mechanisms, although promising, are often impractical due to excessive power and computational requirements. As a result, cybersecurity is frequently deprioritized in favour of operational performance and efficiency, leaving IoD devices exposed across software, hardware, and communication layers. This reality is compounded by market pressures that prioritize feature-rich deployments over secure-by-design architectures, particularly in non-military applications.

One of the significant observations from this survey is that the majority of published research on UAV and IoD cybersecurity occurred between 2020 and 2022, with a noticeable decline in new studies during 2023 and 2025. This temporal gap highlights the need for renewed research focus and innovation, especially as the scale and complexity of IoD deployments continue to grow.

Beyond identifying threats, this survey also provides an in-depth analysis of the strengths and limitations of existing countermeasures. Both defensive and offensive techniques, including anti-drone systems for detecting and neutralizing rogue UAVs, are examined alongside proactive measures such as threat modeling. Notably, threat modeling emerges as a practical and adaptive

¹⁴<https://hakshop.myshopify.com/products/wifi-pineapple>

¹⁵<https://www.techtarget.com/searchsecurity/definition/Wi-Fi-Pineapple>

approach for understanding complex attack surfaces and guiding the design of layered security solutions. The review considers a diverse array of threat modeling frameworks, many of which have been tailored to the specific requirements of UAVs and IoD, while others—such as models originally developed for UGVs, can be adapted with limited modification due to architectural similarities.

Despite progress in the field, several research gaps and opportunities remain open. One critical direction for future work is the robust integration of advanced cybersecurity techniques, including AI-powered intrusion detection, lightweight cryptographic schemes, and distributed ledger technologies, directly into autonomous IoD systems. Such integration must account for strict energy, latency, and computational constraints, requiring interdisciplinary innovation in both hardware and software. For instance, recent advances in federated learning and edge AI offer promising avenues for deploying intelligent detection systems without excessive data transmission or energy drain, yet their real-world application in UAV swarms and autonomous missions remains limited.

Furthermore, high-stakes IoD applications, including disaster response, emergency management, and critical infrastructure surveillance, present unique and heightened security requirements. In these domains, a successful cyberattack could have immediate and severe real-world consequences, potentially affecting public safety, national security, or the continuity of essential services. Future research should therefore focus on designing fail-safe, resilient cybersecurity frameworks that support operational continuity and rapid recovery, even in hostile or unpredictable environments. This may involve the exploration of self-healing protocols, dynamic trust management, or hybrid architectures that maintain functionality even when individual nodes are compromised.

Cross-layer security is another pressing area for further investigation. Given the tightly coupled nature of IoD architectures, an attack on a single layer can propagate and disrupt higher-level mission objectives. Future work should address the development of holistic security models that enable early detection and proactive mitigation across all architectural layers, including physical, data link, network, and application. Such efforts may benefit from advanced ML techniques that model inter-layer dependencies and predict potential attack paths, or from adaptive access control mechanisms that respond to real-time risk assessments.

A persistent and foundational gap identified by this survey is the lack of robust, standardized methodologies for quantitative and qualitative risk assessment in IoD. There is an urgent need for widely accepted metrics, datasets, and evaluation frameworks that enable benchmarking and comparison across proposed solutions. The research community would benefit from collaborative initiatives to share threat intelligence, simulation environments, and real-world datasets that accurately reflect the evolving nature of IoD threats. Similarly, there is a need for automated, dynamic risk assessment and mitigation strategies that can keep pace with the rapidly changing threat landscape.

Another important identified challenge that requires significant attention is the lack of interoperability and standardization concerning the deployment of secure IoD systems. The diversity of devices, vendors, and protocols often leads to insecure interfaces and fragmented defences. Future research should prioritize the development and adoption of open, adaptive security standards, including frameworks such as Zero Trust and collaborative trust management systems, to facilitate secure multi-vendor integration and reliable operation at scale.

Consequently, although IoD cybersecurity has advanced considerably, this survey identifies persistent gaps, challenges, and opportunities. Addressing them requires multidisciplinary collaboration, innovation in both fundamental and applied research, and sustained integration of security across the IoD technology lifecycle. With focused efforts, the research community can

enable safer and more resilient UAV and IoD deployments, supporting their responsible use in critical societal applications.

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